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Research Article

A COMPARATIVE STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFICACY AND SAFETY OF TOPICAL GLYCERYL TRINITRATE VS ORAL NIFEDIPINE IN THE TREATMENT OF IDIOPATHIC PERNOSIS.

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Abstract:

Objective: To compare the efficacy and safety of topical glyceryl trinitrate (0.4% cream) and oral nifedipine (10mg/day) in the treatment of idiopathic perniosis.

Method: The present study was conducted on 40 patients divided into two groups A (n=20) and B (n=20). Patients in group A received treatment with topical glyceryl trinitrate (0.4% cream) while patients in group B were treated with oral nifedipine (10mg/dl) for four weeks. Patients in both groups were evaluated for improvement in signs and symptoms i.e. efficacy as well as side effects, every 15 days for twelve weeks.

Results: A total of 40 patients were included in the study but only 32 patients completed the study, 8 patients lost to follow up.

Patients in group B have a higher rate of complete clearance of lesion. Eleven out of seventeen (64.71%) patients in group A whereas fourteen out of fifteen (93.33%) patients in group B had complete clearance of lesion in one month. Clearance of lesion was achieved earlier in group B as compared to in group A.

The relapse rate during two months (off from medication) follow up in group B is low as compared to group A. The side effects are reported higher in group B as compared to group A.

Conclusion: Oral nifedipine leads to earlier and complete clearance of lesion and the relapse rate is low, but side effects are reported higher in that group. Whereas 0.4% of glyceryl trinitrate cream is an effective and safe alternative treatment option for treating idiopathic perniosis.

Keywords: Perniosis, chilblains, nifedipine, glyceryl trinitrate, idiopathic.

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INTRODUCTION:

Idiopathic Perniosis also called chilblains is a benign condition infrequently encountered in clinical practice (1). This term is applied to the cold-induced eruption of painful or pruritic erythematous or violaceous acral papular or nodular lesions(2). Perniosis is either idiopathic or secondary to an underlying disease(16). Genetic predisposition, Female sex, and low body mass index are important risk factors for idiopathic perniosis(1). In perniosis, there is persistent vasoconstriction of deep cutaneous arterioles with vasodilation of smaller superficial vessels. (4). Histopathological changes are nonspecific and include papillary dermal edema with a predominantly mononuclear perivascular and perieccrine infiltrate. (7,8). Prophylactic warming of acral areas, achieved by heat and appropriate clothing, best prevents perniosis(16). In most patients, it is a self-limiting disease and lesions resolve in 2-3 weeks duration(4). But in some patients, it can lead to severe swelling and sometimes even ulceration which impair their quality of life. Vasodilators are the mainstay of treatment in such patients. (13).

Oral nifedipine has been proved to be effective in relieving symptoms of perniosis in a double-blind, placebo-controlled trial and an open study. (17) However, the potential side effects of oral nifedipine particularly those affecting the cardiovascular system call for cautious use. Glyceryl trinitrate is a nitric oxide donor that produces endothelial independent vasodilatation and has been shown to increase digital blood flow in patients with primary Raynaud's phenomenon and limited cutaneous systemic sclerosis. (18).

This study aims to compare the efficacy and safety of oral nifedipine to that of topical glyceryl trinitrate. To treat patients effective but lesser bothering treatment option.

METHODS AND MATERIAL:

This prospective comparative study was carried out in a tertiary care hospital over a period of four months after taking approval from the institution's ethical committee. 70 patients were enrolled in the study. Complete blood counts, ANA, and RA factor were carried out to rule out systemic causes of perniosis. All eligible patients (n=40) according to inclusion and exclusion criteria were recruited.

Inclusion criteria:

Patients with IP defined as inflammatory lesions (erythema, cyanosis, macules, papules, nodules, or ulcers) involving an acral area (hands, feet, or face)

associated with itching, pain, or tingling sensations along with a history of exposure to cold (the diagnosis was made clinically by a consultant dermatologist), both male and female patients and patients who gave written informed consent to participate in the trial.

Exclusion criteria:

Patients with any systemic disease, history of Raynaud's phenomenon, taking any topical or systemic medication, pregnant or lactating females, patients under 12 years or above 60 years of age, blood pressure below 110/70 mmHg, and patients with positive ANA or RA factor.

Informed consent was taken from all patients. A detailed baseline examination of lesions and severity was made by a consultant dermatologist and patients were briefed about the whole process. Eligible patients are randomly divided into two groups. Patients in group A were instructed to gently massage a thin layer of glyceryl trinitrate 0.4% cream to the affected area twice a day. Patients in group B were started with nifedipine 10 mg/day.

They were evaluated for improvement in signs and symptoms and any side effects, every 15 days by the same consultant, for six weeks. Complete resolution of signs and symptoms was taken as the endpoint. The primary outcome was efficacy and the secondary outcome was side effects. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 17. The therapeutic effects of the two treatments were compared using a t-test and chi-square test. P-value <0.05(confidence interval of 95%) was taken as significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 40 patients were included in the study but only 32 patients completed the study, 8 patients lost to follow up.

Patients in group B have a higher rate of complete clearance of lesion. Eleven out of seventeen (64.71%) patients in group A whereas fourteen out of fifteen (93.33%) patients in group B had complete clearance of lesion in one month. (p-value = .05) Clearance of lesion was achieved earlier (8±4 days) in group B as compared to (15±3 days) in group A. (p-value = .06) The relapse rate during two months (off from medication) follow up in group B (n=1) is low as compared to group A (n=6). (p-value = .05)

The side effects are reported higher in group B i.e. headache (n=7) and postural dizziness (n=5) as compared to group A in which headache is reported by (n=2) patients (p-value = .02) and postural hypotension by (n=1), (p-value = .04).

Table 1 Demographic profile of the study population

	No. of patients	Percentage
Age group		
<25 years	19	47.5
25-30	16	40
30-35	5	12.5
>35	10	25
Gender		
Male	13	32.5
Female	27	67.5
BMI		
Under 18.5	16	40
18.5-24.9	19	47.5
24.9-29.9	10	25
> 29.9	5	12.5
Severity		
Mild	14	35
Moderate	18	45
Severe	8	20
Area of involvement		
Hands		
Hands and feet	25	62.5
Hands, feet, and face	15	37.5
	0	0

P-value calculated by the chi-square test

Table 2 Comparison in terms of outcome and side effects between two groups

Outcome	Group A (n=20)	Group B (n=20)	P-value
Complete clearance of the lesion	11	14	.05
Relapse rate during two month follow up	6	1	.05
Average time taken for clearance of the lesion	8 ± 4	15 ± 3	.06
Side effects			
Headache	2	7	.02
Postural dizziness	1	5	.04
Lost to follow up	3	5	.42

P-value calculated by chi-square test

DISCUSSION:

Many studies published in the recent past indicate that idiopathic perniosis is not an uncommon presentation in South East Asian countries during winters. (13) It is considered to be more common in young females, usually with a low BMI. (1,2) This was also reflected in our study with 67.5% of the patients being females. Sixteen patients (40%) were underweight. All were nonsmokers.

This randomized controlled study showed that clinical outcome in patients with Idiopathic perniosis using oral nifedipine is not significantly different from those using glyceryl trinitrate cream (0.4%) in terms of complete clearance of lesions. However, with systemic nifedipine, the response is quicker. This can be explained based on the mode of delivery of the drug. Multiple factors such as the amount of GTN cream applied, frequency of hand washing and wet work may have affected the results of group A.

In the double-blind, placebo-controlled trial by Dowd *et al.*(13) establishing nifedipine as the drug of choice for perniosis in 1986, 10 patients receiving nifedipine had complete clearance of lesions within 7-10 days, whereas in our study the mean duration of clearance of lesions with nifedipine is 8 ± 4 days even with a much lower dose i.e. 10mg/day as compared to 60mg/day in a study by Dowd *et al.*(19) In the open study by Rustin *et al.*(17) the duration of clearance of lesions was much longer; mean 21 days for lesions on hands and feet and 23 days for lesions on feet alone. The reason was that only 17 of the 31 patients could tolerate a dose up to 40 mg/day of nifedipine. (13)

In another trial comparing nifedipine with diltiazem by Patra *et al.*(14) patients showed 80-90% improvement in signs and symptoms of perniosis with 30-40mg of nifedipine in the Indian population. Only one patient in this study developed dizziness with nifedipine at this dose. However, in our study 7 patients developed a headache. One reason may be that most of the patients in the study by Patra *et al.*(20) were adult males (M: F=18:7) including soldiers whereas in our study majority of the patients were young females (M: F=29:5) with a mean BMI of 21 ± 3.8 in the group receiving nifedipine. In group A, only one patient developed mild local irritation with glyceryl trinitrate cream that settled within a few hours without any treatment.

In a study by Anderson *et al.*(18) on patients with primary Raynaud's phenomenon and limited cutaneous sclerosis, glyceryl trinitrate cream proved to increase digital blood flow when measured by laser Doppler imaging. (11) The same mechanism

that produces increased digital blood flow in Raynaud's phenomenon and systemic sclerosis i.e. nitric oxide-induced vasodilatation seems to be effective in patients with idiopathic perniosis, as well.

Glyceryl trinitrate topical preparation in combination with calcium channel blockers is advocated in Raynaud's phenomenon, particularly in cases not responding to calcium channel blockers alone. (16) Occasional mention of glyceryl trinitrate cream as a treatment of idiopathic perniosis can be found. (14) Pilot studies with nitroglycerine ointment for the prevention of cold injuries have been conducted on soldiers and workers residing at high altitude with good results in India. (13) The results of our study clearly indicate a place for glyceryl trinitrate cream in the treatment options for idiopathic perniosis.

CONCLUSION:

Topical glyceryl trinitrate 0.4% cream is an effective and safe alternative to oral nifedipine in the treatment of idiopathic perniosis. Systemic nifedipine leads to clearance of lesions earlier than topical glyceryl trinitrate cream.

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